

MEASURING CREATIVE ECONOMIES: EXISTING MODELS & THE DISCE APPROACH

A Horizon 2020 project by:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822314

MEASURING CREATIVE ECONOMIES: EXISTING MODELS & THE DISCE APPROACH

Project number:	822314
Project name:	Developing Inclusive and Sustainable Creative Economies
Project acronym:	DISCE
Deliverable number:	D2.1
Deliverable name:	Current state of knowledge on the CCIs
Work Package:	WP2
Responsible partner:	GSSI
Author:	Alessandro Crociata
Type:	Report
Due date:	June 2019

To be cited: Crociata, A. (2019) *Measuring creative economies: Existing models & the DISCE Approach*. DISCE Publications. Published online: <https://disce.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/DISCE-Report-D2.1.pdf>

Executive summary

The overarching research question for DISCE is, 'What are inclusive and sustainable creative economies, and how can they be developed?' Each of the work packages has a specific role to play in answering this question, and WP2 is tasked with considering issues of quantitative data. The approach of DISCE is to combine both conceptual and empirical inquiry. As part of the overall research design, WP2 has a specific role in helping to identify and analyse the range of data that is currently used in processes of modelling and analysing the 'creative economy' across Europe. However, part of the specific approach of DISCE is to rethink what we might mean by 'inclusivity' and 'sustainability', and to ask: what are 'creative economies'. In this context, the role of WP2 is not only to analyse existing data within the frameworks of existing models of the creative economy, but to work closely with other work packages to identify and analyse new sources of data on the basis of DISCE's reconceptualization of inclusive and sustainable creative economies. Working closely with the other DISCE work packages, WP2 will thereby work to develop new approaches to modelling, mapping and measuring creative economies across the EU.

There are a number of interesting and important methodological challenges that WP2 faces in undertaking this work. One of these is the fragmentation of the definitions and approaches with which the creative economy is currently analysed. A range of different taxonomies are employed by different agencies and researchers, applying these approaches at a range of geographical scales. Additionally, because DISCE is specifically aiming to

rethink 'inclusivity' and 'sustainability' - including, for example, reopening the question of the boundaries of the creative economy - the process of identifying and analysing what data is relevant and usable is a complex one, to which DISCE is taking a deliberately iterative approach. Within this research design, part of WP2's role is not only to analyse currently available data for the creative economy in Europe, but also to assess the relevance and value of these data in relation to the overall DISCE research question.

Overall, then, playing these different roles, WP2 is working closely with other work packages to answer the DISCE research question, by helping to identify new approaches to quantitative data within an overall reconceptualization of inclusive and sustainable creative economies. The aim of this initial WP2 report is to briefly summarise a series of influential models of the creative economy that have provided the basis for previous processes of measurement and mapping - establishing the context within which DISCE is developing its own approach to modelling, mapping and measuring the creative economy, beyond these existing frameworks. The report concludes by indicating the approach that the DISCE research project will take, beyond the existing models of the creative economy, and what implications this will have for the collection of data in the future.

Existing Models for Mapping and Measuring the Creative Economy

Developing Inclusive & Sustainable Creative Economies (DISCE) is an interdisciplinary, mixed-methods project. The overall research design combines case studies of the creative economies in ten European cities, in combination with analysis of pan-European data. (Our overall research design is discussed in more detail in other outputs.) One of the central aims of the project is to use this combination of methods to reconceptualise 'inclusive and sustainable creative economies', and to develop new approaches to statistical analyses, mapping and modelling of creative economies in Europe.

A key starting point for DISCE is the need for more conceptually and empirically robust statistical descriptions of the sector, to capture not only its size and 'economic' profile (in terms of conventional economic measures such as employment and Gross Value Added), but also its broader dynamics and social value in contemporary society. A central challenge for DISCE is how to develop a new approach such as this, whilst also providing a quantitative basis for an EU-wide comparative framework: capable of dealing with the different characteristics and values of creative economies in Europe - not only narrowly 'economic' value but also in terms of broader social value - whilst being also being practical.

Taxonomies and Definitions

Despite the fact that the European Commission has previously provided a definition of the Creative and Cultural Industries (CCIs) and that the sector has actually been sized (EC, 2010a; 2012), within the DISCE project there is an explicit recognition of the need to advance towards "a comprehensive understanding of CCIs, improving indicators at national and at EU level" (H2020 Work Programme 2018-2020). Developing conceptually and empirically robust definitions, characterizations, and measurements of the creative economy is an unsolved issue for those seeking to develop a comprehensive policy scheme to support the creative economy. For the purpose of DISCE, the plurality of models and definitions of the creative economy is an important starting point.

There is currently no official and universally agreed statistical definition of the creative economy. On the contrary, a significant definitional debate has developed, and over the past twenty years, a plethora of closely related terms have been employed. These include the culture industry, the cultural industries, the creative industries, cultural-products industries, the creative economy, and the cultural economy, together forming an imprecise muddle (Boggs, 2009). Some refer to all of these as CCIs (e.g. Chuluunbaatar et al., 2013) while others see differences between them (see Jones et al., 2016).

As Justin O'Connor's historical overview of the discourse indicates (O'Connor 2010), this range of related and competing terms are not neutral: they are embedded within political and policy debates. Famously, the seminal work of Adorno and Horkheimer (1947) introduced the term 'the culture industry' to refer to industrially produced commercial entertainment such as broadcasting, film, publishing, recorded music, in opposition to the subsidised "arts" such as visual and performing arts, museums and galleries. The Frankfurt School writers were, of course, using the term 'the culture industries' pejoratively: emphasising the new ideological functions that mass entertainment was playing within capitalistic systems of socio-economic relations. Contrastingly, during the 1980s, the term 'cultural industries' was employed in the UK with quite a different political inflection: indicating the 'democratic' possibilities for promoting forms of popular cultural production within progressive public policy (Garnham 1985; Loosely 2011; Street 2011).

A key moment in the history of these terms is the work of the UK's New Labour government, following its victory in the general election of 1997. With the creation of the Department of Media Culture and Sport (DCMS), the first Creative Industries Mapping Document was written (DCMS, 1998), providing the first definition - and the first measurement - of the creative industries, and identifying them as among the legitimate objects of national public policy. This document does not refer to 'cultural industries', but to creative industries, identified as: "those industries which have their origin in individual creativity, skills and talent and which have a potential for wealth and job creation through the generation and exploitation of intellectual property" (DCMS, 1998: 3). Additionally, the document identifies the thirteen sub-sectors that make up the creative industries. These are: "advertising, architecture, the art and antiques market, crafts, design, designer fashion, film, interactive leisure software, music, the performing arts, publishing, software and television and radio." (DCMS 1998: 3)

The definition of the creative industries provided by the UK government has proven enormously influential internationally. However, there have since been a range of criticisms made of the DCMS definition (see Garnham 2005; Galloway and Dunlop 2007; Banks and O'Connor 2009), a reflection on the developments in terminology (Gross 2020) and an ongoing discussion on modelling and statistical approaches (Ortega-Villa & Ley-Garcia, 2018).

During the last few years, a new approach in classifying cultural and creative industries has emerged, based on an assessment of the contribution that CCIs make to the whole economy. Amongst others, with the assumption that CCIs boost the wider economy, in 2008 NESTA provided the so-called 'Creative Trident' model that has as its main aim disentangling the creative 'added value'. This approach is known as the employment-based classification, and its rationale is that it considers the activities which are part of creative occupations for the production of cultural and non-cultural goods and services – each of which are considered to be a part of the creative economy.

The model counts the number of people employed in creative activities and industries bringing together those working in the creative industries and those working with creative tasks (and skills) in other firms and organizations. The model focus “on three types of employment: ‘specialist’ artists, professionals or creative individuals working in creative industries; ‘support’ staff in those industries providing management, secretarial, administrative or accountancy back-up; and creative individuals ‘embedded’ in other industries not defined as ‘creative’.” (Higgs et al., 2008: 3).

A further consideration must be made on the consequences of a given definition of CCIs perimeter. The consequences of any classification of what is or is not cultural and creative industries, deserve attention as it defines the legal and budgetary scope of action for policy makers. Theoretical and methodological assumptions have clear consequences in the way those activities and the people behind them are treated consequently in terms of subsidies, policy support measures et similia.

The rationale behind a classification should the support evidence-based decision making, allows comparisons over time, between policies, countries and regions, social groups and industries, and contributes to increased transparency and accountability (Eurostat, 2014). European Commission supports these sectors by moving from Eurostat’s work as part of European Statistical System (ESS)-net Culture. But at the same time EC deals with such issue and is boosting a critical reflection toward a further harmonisation of taxonomies and statistics on the cultural and creative sectors (see D2.2)

UNESCO, UNCTAD and Other International Models

Creative Economy Reports published by two specialised bodies of the UNESCO and UNCTAD have contributed notably in pushing the CCIs to the global level (See De Beukealaer 2015; De Beukealaer and Spence 2019).

Figure 1. UNCTAD classification of creative industries (UNDP/UNCTAD, 2008, 14)

The UNCATC/UNESCO 2008 classification provides a framework which categorises the CCIs across four groups, hailing the potential of the cultural and creative industries for development:

- Heritage (including cultural sites and traditional cultural expressions)
- Arts (including performing and visual arts)
- Media (including publishing and audio-visuals)
- Functional creations (including new media, design and creative services).

This model is layered in terms of four main pillars. First, the CCIs serve to promote of the diversity of cultural expressions within the global circulation of cultural expressions. Second, CCIs are a driver of economic growth in terms of job opportunity and export diversification. Third, CCIs are at the base of development pathways beyond economic terms focusing on the social and human aspects before economic aspects.

Among the other international documents on the subject, those published by UNESCO (1986), Eurostat (2000), OECD (2005 and 2006) and the European Community (2006) deserve special attention. UNESCO proposes a classification of the categories to be considered for the production of cultural statistics, based on nine categories of sectors and five functions in the “cultural production process”. The nine categories are:

(1) cultural heritage; (2) printed matter and literature; (3) music; (4) performing arts; (5) audio media; (6) audiovisual media; (7) socio-cultural activities; (8) sports and games, and (9) environment and nature. The five functions of the cultural production process are: (1) creation, (2) production, (3) distribution, (4) consumption and (5) preservation.

The fragmentation of the definitions in the approaches used, as well as the different meanings that each of them carries with it, led the European Union to produce a document of international interest elaborated by Eurostat’s Leg Group (2000). The main objective of this document is to harmonize cultural statistics in order to carry out comparative analyses on the cultural sectors of the countries of the European Community. To determine a common definition of the cultural sector, the Leg Group starts from the UNESCO framework, but departs from it by reducing the descriptive parameters, i.e. by eliminating the categories sport and games, and environment and nature. Eight domains are therefore identified:

(1) artistic and monumental heritage, (2) archives, (3) libraries, (4) books and press, (5) visual arts, (6) architecture, (7) performing arts, (8) audio and audiovisual media/multimedia, and six functions to define the economic activities of the cultural sector: (1) preservation, (2) creation, (3) production, (4) dissemination, (5) trade/sales and (6) education.

In 2006 the KEA European Affairs Report attempts to measure the contribution of the cultural and creative sector to growth and cohesion in Europe by establishing a correspondence between the sector and its activities. In this piece, the cultural sector is basically split into 1) a non-industrial sector where non-reproducible goods and services are produced and consumed in the same moment. This category includes the field of arts such as: crafts, painting, sculpture, photography, theatre, dance, circus, festivals, museums, libraries, archaeological sites, archives.; 2) an industrial sector where reproducible goods are produced for mass consumption and distribution. This category represents cultural industries such as: film industry, radio, video games, live music, and publishing.

In a review of the most widely used approaches, cultural economist David Throsby (2007) presents six different taxonomic models (see Table 1). He includes the categories that each approach considers, according to the principles on which its classification system is based.

Table 1. Taxonomic approaches

- 1. DCMS model** (UK Department of Culture, Media and Sport, *The Creative Industries Mapping Document 2001*, London: DCMS, 2001). Based on activities requiring creativity, skill and talent, with potential for wealth and job creation through exploitation of their intellectual property.
- 2. Symbolic texts model** (David Hesmondhalgh, *The Cultural Industries*, London: Sage, 2002). Based on industries concerned with industrial production and dissemination of symbolic texts.
- 3. Concentric circles model** (David Throsby, *Economics and Culture*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001). Based on origin and diffusion of creative ideas in sound, text and image from core creative arts.
- 4. WIPO copyright model** (World Intellectual Property Organisation, *Guide on Surveying the Economic Contribution of the Copyright-based Industries*, Geneva: WIPO, 2003). Based on industries involved directly or indirectly in the creation, manufacture, production, broadcast and distribution of copyrighted works.
- 5. UIS trade-related model** (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, *International Flows of Selected Cultural Goods and Services 1994–2003: Defining and Capturing the Flows of Global Cultural Trade*, Montreal: UIS, 2005). Based on cultural goods and services entering international trade.
- 6. Americans for the Arts model** (Americans for the Arts, *Creative Industries 2005: The Congressional Report*, Washington DC: Americans for the Arts, 2005). Based on businesses involved with the production or distribution of the arts (“arts-centric businesses”).

Source: Throsby, 2007

Quantitative data and DISCE concerns

Modelling and Mapping Inclusive and Sustainable Creative economies: What is Being Measured?

DISCE highlights a need for an inclusive understanding of the sector. This takes a broad view of the creative economy that questions the models outlined above. In other DISCE reports we describe in more detail our objections to the existing models. One of the headline points to emphasise here is that we are taking an 'ecological' approach (Holden 2015; Wilson et al. 2017; Wilson and Gross 2017; Gross and Wilson 2018, 2019) to the creative economy: paying attention to a wide range of material and immaterial resources, and their interconnections. Moreover, being open to the idiosyncrasy and variety of these eco-systems, we employ the term economies, in the plural.

In developing this approach, WP2 is working closely with other work packages to identify what kinds of data are relevant and useful to understanding 'inclusive and sustainable creative economies' within the re-conceptualised account being developed. We will be exploring a wide range of potential data related to questions of creative education; creative work; creative entrepreneurship; business models; and a wide range of other aspects of life within the cities we are studying. This will take us far beyond conventional measures of employment figures, GDP / GVA, and export measures. Instead, we are working towards the development of a cultural development index, drawing on the capability approach (Sen 1999; Nussbaum 2011; Robeyns 2017; Gross and Wilson 2018), which has at its heart the questions: what kinds of lives can people live? What can people be and do? We discuss this overall approach in other research outputs, including the WP5 literature review, and the Inception Report Case Study Framework (D3.1, D4.1, D5.1).

REFERENCES

- Americans for the Arts, 2005.** Creative industries 2005: The congressional report [online]. Americans for the Arts. Available from: https://www.americansforthearts.org/sites/default/files/pdf/about_us/2005AmericansForTheArtsAnnualReport.pdf [Accessed 30 October 2019].
- Banks, M. & O'Connor, J.. (2009)** 'After the creative industries', *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 15:4, 365-373, DOI: 10.1080/10286630902989027
- De Beukealaer, C. (2015)** *Cultural Development: Learning from the Palimpsest of Practice*. Amsterdam: European Cultural Foundation.
- De Beukealaer, C. and Spence, K. M. (2019)** *Global Cultural Economy*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Department of Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS).** 1998. *Creative Industries Mapping Document*.
- DCMS (2001)** *The Creative Industries Mapping Document*, United Kingdom.
- Eurostat (2000)** *Cultural Statistics in the EU. Final Report of the LEG*, Eurostat working papers, Luxembourg.
- EUROSTAT. (2010)** *Cultural Statistics*. Pocketbook Edition.
- EUROSTAT (2014)** *Towards a harmonised methodology for statistical indicators. Part 1: Indicator typologies and terminologies*. Collection: Manuals and guidelines. Publications Office of the European Union: Luxembourg
- Garnham, N. (1987).** "Concepts of Culture: Public Policy and the Cultural Industries." In *Studies in Culture: An Introductory Reader*, ed. Ann Gray and Jim McGuigan. London: Arnold, 1997, pp. 54-61.
- Gross, J. (2020, Forthcoming).** *The Birth of the Creative Industries Revisited: An Oral History of the 1998 DCMS Mapping Document*. London: King's College London.
- Gross, J. and Wilson, N. (2018)** "Cultural Democracy: An Ecological and Capabilities Approach". *International Journal of Cultural Policy*. DOI: 10.1080/10286632.2018.1538363

- Gross, J. and Wilson, N. (2019)** *Creating the Environment: The Cultural Ecosystems of Creative People and Places*. Creative People and Places. <http://www.creativepeopleplaces.org.uk/our-learning/creating-environment>
- Galloway, S. and Dunlop, S. (2007)** 'A Critique of Definitions of The Cultural and Creative Industries In Public Policy', *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 13:1, 17-31, DOI: 10.1080/10286630701201657
- Garnham, N. (2005)** 'From cultural to creative industries', *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 11:1, 15-29, DOI: 10.1080/10286630500067606
- Hesmondhalgh, D. (2002)**, *The Cultural Industries*, London: Sage.
- Higgs, P. L., Cunningham, S. D., & Bakhshi, H. (2008)**. *Beyond the creative industries: Mapping the creative economy in the United Kingdom*.
- Holden, J. (2015)** *The Ecology of Culture*. Swindon: Arts and Humanities Research Council.
- Horkheimer, M. & Adorno, T. W. (1944)** *Dialectic of Enlightenment: Philosophical Fragments* Accessed in October 2019 https://monoskop.org/images/2/27/Horkheimer_Max_Adorno_Theodor_W_Dialectic_of_Enlightenment_Philosophical_Fragments.pdf
- KEA European Affairs. (2006)**. *The Economy of Culture in Europe*. Bruxelles, Belgium: KEA for the European Commission.
- KEA European Affairs. (2009)**. The impact of culture on creativity. *KEA European Affairs*.
- Looseley, D. (2011)**. "Notions of popular culture in cultural policy: A comparative history of France and Britain." *International Journal of Cultural Policy* 17 (4): 365-379.
- Markusen A., Wassall G., Denatale D. and Cohen R. (2008)** Defining the creative economy: industry and occupational approaches, *Economic Development Quarterly* 22(1), 24-45.
- O'Connor J., (2007)**, *The cultural and creative industries: a review of the literature*, Report for Creative Partnerships, School of Performance and Cultural industries The University of Leeds.

- O'Connor, J. (2010)** *The Cultural and Creative Industries: A Literature Review*. Second Edition. Newcastle: Creativity, Culture and Education.
- Ortega-Villa, L. M., & Ley-Garcia, J. (2018)**. Analysis of Cultural Indicators: A Comparison of Their Conceptual Basis and Dimensions. *Social Indicators Research*, 137 (2), 413–439.
- Pratt A. C., (2004)**, The cultural economy. A call for spazialized production of culture. *International Journal of Cultural studies*, SAGE Publication, London.
- Pratt, A. C. 2009**. “Policy Transfer and the Field of the Cultural and Creative Industries: What Can Be Learned from Europe?” In *Creative Economies, Creative Cities*, edited by Lily Kong and Justin O'Connor, 98:9–23. Dordrecht, the Netherlands: Springer.
- Street, J. (2011)**. “The popular, the diverse and the excellent: political values and UK cultural policy.” *International Journal of Cultural Policy* 17 (4): 380-393.
- Throsby, D. (2001)** *Economics and Culture*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Throsby, D. (2008)**. Modelling the cultural industries. *International journal of cultural policy*, 14(3), 217-232.
- UNDP/UNCTAD (2008)**, *Creative economy*. Report 2008, Geneva—New York: UNDP, UNCTAD
- UNESCO. (2005)**. International flows of selected cultural goods and services, 1994–2003. *Defining and Capturing Global Cultural Trade*.
- Wilson, N. and Gross, J. (2017)** *Caring for Cultural Freedom: An Ecological Approach to Supporting Young People’s Cultural Learning*. A New Direction.
- Wilson, N., Gross, J. and Bull, A. (2017)** *Towards Cultural Democracy: Promoting Cultural Capabilities for Everyone*. King’s College London.
- World Intellectual Property Organization. (2003)**. *Guide on surveying the economic contribution of the copyright-based industries*. Geneva: World Intellectual Property Organization.